

IMPROVING THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIO-CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES BASED ON THE TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACH

Mahmudova Sumbula Abdumalikovna

Researcher of Fergana State University

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Abstract: In this article, theoretical-methodological foundations of social-creative competence development in future pedagogues, cognitive-methodical system of social-creative competence development and development of social activity skills and creative competence in future pedagogues in the conditions of reforms are studied. Also, the integrative methodology of development of socio-creative competence was analyzed on the example of Pedagogical sciences.

Key words: pedagogic, social-creative, competence, cognitive-methodical, social activity, skill, qualification, competence, integrative approach, development, pedagogical model, reproductive, functional.

INTRODUCTION. Regular improvement of the development of socio-creative competence in future pedagogues based on the technological approach is considered as one of the issues that must be resolved in order to achieve the strategic goals of education. As the social life of the society develops in connection with the processes of globalization, this development is also reflected in the educational process.

The technological approach requires future pedagogues not to acquire knowledge and skills individually, but to acquire them as a whole. In connection with this demand, in turn, the system of choosing teaching methods will be changed. The selection of teaching methods and their application in the practical process require the improvement of competencies that meet the requirements of the educational process. The technological approach is also considered important for the technologicalization of education and the evaluation of the quality of its results.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Issues of development of social activity among future pedagogues in Uzbekistan M. Rakhmanova, M. Kuronov, Kh. Tojiboyeva, G. J. Tulenova, Q. Quranboyev; N. Abdumuratova, D. Nafasovlar studied the development of social competence, while N. Azizkho'jayeva, A. Aripdzhanova, G. Ibragimova studied the aspects of teaching students to work creatively and developing different competencies in them. In the research works of N. Muslimov, O'. Tolipov, F. Exsonova, the problems of creative education were studied by M. Kadirova, Sh. Pozilova, A. Khalikov, Sh. Sharipov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The most generalized approach to modeling in modern conditions is related to the development of systems science and their integration with the methodology of models. As a result of this association, a special field of model knowledge - system modeling was formed. Theoretically, it is based on the general methodological rules of the systems approach and universal modeling parameters developed in the scientific research of the field of knowledge.

In understanding the training of social pedagogues, we rely on scientific ideas about the "pedagogical system", for this the starting point is the general scientific concept of the "system". Today, several hundred definitions of this concept can be found in scientific literature. The term "system" is used in scientific literature in different meanings. Often, the term "system" is understood as a set of components that create new qualities that are not inherent to its components.

The concept of "pedagogical system" is clarified through the study of "productive pedagogical activity", it is related to the concept of "pedagogical process", which is based on the interaction of students and teachers. An effective pedagogical system is aimed at achieving the goal and leads to a pre-planned change of circumstances, changing the characteristics and qualities of students. According to the scientist, the pedagogical system is defined as an independent phenomenon of educational practice, and it is characterized by five structural elements: purpose, educational information, means of communication, students and teachers. In order to describe pedagogical activity in the most general, invariant form in these social conditions, a very broad concept of "pedagogical system" is used.

The general requirements for the models in the development of the conceptual model of the system for the development of socio-creative competence in future pedagogues are as follows:

- having qualities such as completeness, adequacy and gradualness; providing the possibility of large-scale changes and additions for the redevelopment of a social object, event, process;
 - to focus on implementation using existing opportunities, that is, to carry out activities at a certain level of social development;
 - providing new useful information about a social object (event, process) according to the research task;
 - to check the compliance of one's activity with the studied social object, event, process.
- The main criteria for evaluating models:
- newness of reflection (intuitive, qualitative description, visual imitation, reproduction of the system);
 - distribution (in general social sphere, industry, social group, etc.), level of development (an idea is promoted, a scheme is built, an algorithm is developed, etc.).

Development of an improved model of the teaching system focused on the development methodology of socio-creative competence in future pedagogues based on the requirements of the time, determination of the educational style and development strategy of professors and teachers suitable for students, classification of various pedagogical tools and methods, enables the use of existing resources and other supporting materials.

This model includes 4 components. The main goal of the model, defined in the "Maqsad" blog, is to improve the methodology of social-creative competence development by organizing classes based on the integration of "Creative pedagogy" and "Social pedagogy" disciplines. The goal is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, state education based on the competence approach of higher education as the legal and normative basis of the social order. cited in the standard. The purpose of education determines the essence of education, expresses the needs of society and envisages its development. The goal of education is defined on the basis of the learning process, its essence,

content, methods and tools, professor-teacher and student relations, and the system's efficiency indicator represents the formation of a person or specialist. The main issue facing the education system today and in the future is characterized by what kind of person and specialist should be trained for the development of society, that is, a person should be formed who meets certain requirements set in the educational process.

The model for the development of socio-creative competence of future pedagogues, created within the framework of the research, is organized as a whole and open, and it allows to direct the system of development of social-creative competence in future pedagogues to the goal, to determine the compatibility of the set goal with the result.

The content-technological blog includes "Content" and "Technological Basics". The first of these is the "Content" component, which defines the content of the model to achieve the goal. As a means of achieving the goal, it is to apply a technological approach to the teaching of the subjects selected in the course of our research to social skills and creativity in future pedagogues.

CONCLUSION. Application of modeling for the development of socio-creative competence in future pedagogues at all stages (professional orientation, education, science, career choice and certification, consulting service, etc.) reflected in all stages of development (professional adaptation, professional skills and professional creativity). At each stage, the components of pedagogical activity are determined (specific types of activities managed on the basis of strategic goals and motives, professional actions directed at tactical goals, ways of performing actions in specific conditions and evaluating their effectiveness, etc.), the basis for determining the professional functions of a social sphere pedagogue serves as (motivational, purposeful and fast) and leads to development.

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